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Research article

The green knowledge space: Climate change mitigation technologies in developing countries

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ABSTRACT

Regional studies show that regions develop new technologies related to their existing knowledge base. R&D expenditure targeting sectors related to this knowledge base is, therefore, more promising to create innovative output. Using global patent data, we investigate whether path-dependency of innovation in climate-change mitigation and adaptation technologies (CCMTs) holds at the country level and depends on the country's development level. We study 197 countries during 2005–2018 and find that relatedness is a significant determinant of innovation in CCMTs, with stronger effects for developing countries. We construct a two-mode network linking countries to technological classes based on patenting activity to identify each country's existing knowledge and those CCMTs where they are most likely to innovate. This is valuable for decision-making on R&D spending and especially important for developing countries, which face stringent financial and human capital constraints in technology creation and thus require more targeted investments.

1. Introduction

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are predominantly (63 %) generated by developing countries, which also face 80 % of climate change's social cost (Busch, 2015). However, over 73 % of innovation to mitigate or adapt to climate change takes place in the top 20 % of developed countries.¹ Innovations in climate change mitigation and adaptation technologies (CCMT) that originate in developed countries are rarely diffused to developing countries (Probst et al., 2021). When they do reach developing countries, their impact on climate change mitigation and adaptation is often less effective compared to the outcomes in the countries where they were developed (Ormrod, 1990). Consequently, developing countries would greatly benefit by fostering their own innovation in CCMTs.

However, innovation in CCMTs² is scarce in many developing countries for three main reasons: i) poor protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) (Chen and Puttitanun, 2005; EPO, 2010); ii) low levels of environmental policies yielding little incentives for innovation (Porter and van der Linde, 1995; de Vries and Withagen, 2005; Johnstone et al., 2010); iii) financial and human resource

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E-mail address: franziska.tinnefeld@unicatt.it (F. Tinnefeld).¹ These statistics are based on PATSTAT data over the years 2005–2018. See also Coe et al. (1997) for innovation in general and Aghion et al. (2009b) for climate change mitigation and adaptation technologies.² The term climate change mitigation technologies (CCMTs) is used as an umbrella term that includes (1) technologies with the potential to mitigate climate change, (2) technologies with the potential to adapt to adverse effects caused by climate change, and (3) technologies with the potential to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2024.100944>

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constraints limiting R&D expenditure and knowledge creation (Dakhli and De Clercq, 2004; Aubert, 2005). In this paper, we argue that, despite these constraints, developing countries can increase innovation in CCMTs by focusing on innovations related to their knowledge base, i.e., the set of technologies in which countries hold a relative advantage.

As such, this paper explores how the existing knowledge base influences the likelihood of countries innovating in CCMTs and examines the differences between developed and developing countries in this regard. We use country-level data to analyse a broad range of countries, enabling a more detailed analysis of differences between developed and developing countries - something that regional level analyses does not permit due to data limitations in developing countries.

We investigate if theories on regional technological relatedness and path dependencies in the development of innovation (Boschma and Frenken, 2011) hold at the *country level* for CCMTs and whether there are differences between developed and developing countries. Specifically, we describe a technology space to identify which technologies are most closely related to CCMTs and we empirically test the following hypotheses: H1) The greater the relatedness between a country's knowledge base and a specific CCMT (relatedness density), the more likely the country is to innovate in this class (innovation entry) and the higher its innovation intensity (measured by the number of patents); H2) Technological relatedness plays a greater role in guiding innovation paths in developing than in developed countries, due to the limited ability of developing countries to make radical leaps; H3, H4, H5) Human capital, financial support to R&D, and stringent environmental policies increase innovation in CCMTs (see also Johnstone et al., 2012, for environmental policies).

Our main contribution is to analyse whether the effect of relatedness on innovation entry and innovation intensity of CCMTs depends on a country's economic development stage (hypothesis H2). To study the effect of relatedness on innovation of CCMTs, we use a relatedness measure which, to the best of our knowledge, has not been used on a global scale and a sample of 197 countries over the years 2005- 2018. Identifying whether relatedness affects innovation in CCMTs in developing countries is important for the possible economic benefits it can bring (Aghion et al., 1998; Bilbao-Osorio and Rodriguez-Pose, 2004; Ulku, 2004) and for their need to adapt to and mitigate climate change (see Aghion et al., 2009a; Hasna et al., 2023, for a discussion about innovation and green growth and the benefits of green innovation). Furthermore, developing countries benefit from innovating themselves as there are substantial costs in adapting technologies designed for different contexts (Zanell et al., 2016). We also test the effect of human capital, financial constraints and environmental policies on innovation drawing on previous literature showing that low human capital (Dakhli and De Clercq, 2004) and insufficient R&D investments may harm innovation (Aubert, 2005).

Another contribution is the construction of a unique dataset which uses global patent data employing a technological classification scheme that identifies CCMT classes developed by the European Patent Office (EPO). The dataset permits us to proxy innovation and describe the *technology space*, countries' *knowledge space* and countries' *knowledge base* surrounding 44 classes of CCMTs. We integrate data on technological relatedness from the technology space with the information on countries' knowledge bases to identify which CCMTs hold the greatest potential for countries' innovation effort. To visualise the latter, a two-mode network called *CCMT-potential* connects a country to CCMT's related to its knowledge base.

The *technology space* is a one-mode network whose nodes represent technological classes. Identifying technological classes related to CCMT classes helps measure possible spillovers from a non-CCMT class to a CCMT one. A country's *knowledge base* is the set of technological classes in which a country has a relative technological advantage (RTA), a measure that shows the relative strength of a country in certain technological fields. The measure is comparable to competitive advantage in trade theory. The *knowledge space* is a two-mode network where nodes representing countries are linked to technological classes based on their patenting activity. It visualises each country's knowledge in relation to others. The three network visualisations are made available online for exploration and further research.

Our empirical analysis supports our main hypotheses. We find that relatedness to a country's knowledge base matters for the *entry into* and the *intensity* of CCMTs in a country (H1). The effect of relatedness for the entry in the market is stronger for developing countries than for developed ones while the difference on the intensity of CCMT is small and mainly driven by top innovators in developing countries (H2) (see also Petralia et al., 2017; Perruchas et al., 2020, for general and green innovation, respectively). We also find that human capital is of considerable importance for CCMT innovation (H3), but the role of financial support in R&D is less clear and depends on the model specification (H4). Finally, we do not find evidence regarding the role of environmental policy stringency on CCMT patenting (H5).

We find that CCMTs are related in the technology space to technologies in high engineering, whereas technologies related to human necessities (e.g., "wearing apparel", "footwear", or "food") have very limited potential to contribute to the development of CCMTs. Hence R&D related to high engineering would be more successful than R&D in the food industry which is more distant from CCMTs. Despite many developing countries being specialised in the latter type of industries, we see a strong increase in the relatedness of countries' knowledge bases to CCMTs for not only developed but also developing countries. In fact, while developed countries have seen a decline in CCMT patenting since 2010 - partly due to a policy shift from R&D to the deployment of existing technologies in OECD countries (Cervantes et al., 2023) - developing countries have maintained a relatively stable level of patenting over the past decade.

Our descriptive analysis of the knowledge space and the CCMT potential of countries allows us to explore cross-country differences in terms of their existing knowledge and the relatedness of their knowledge bases to CCMTs. For example, China, the largest emitter of greenhouse gases, has a knowledge base highly related to many CCMTs. The US and Japan, on the other hand, despite substantial patents in CCMTs, have knowledge bases not related to as many CCMTs as China, India, Russia and Iran. Many developing countries have knowledge bases related to CCMTs in the production or processing of goods (Y02P) and CCMTs related to wastewater treatment or waste management (Y02W), reflecting their relative downstream position in value chains.

2. Literature review and theoretical framework

Our measure of relatedness density has been introduced in the global product space literature (see Hidalgo et al., 2007) and developed in the context of regional diversification and regional path dependency by connecting regions to technological classes in which their knowledge is strong (Balland and Rigby, 2017; Balland et al., 2019). The product space is a one-mode network where, using trade data, products are closely linked if they are related.

Knowledge spaces and relatedness of technological classes have been usually employed to study smart specialisation strategies within the EU framework (Balland et al., 2019) and increasingly also focus on green innovation (see Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014; Barbieri et al., 2023, for high-income EU regions and for regions from 33 European countries). Instead, we also consider developing countries, because they are more dependent on branching into related products than developed ones (Petralia et al., 2017; Alshamsi et al., 2018). Indeed, the likelihood of branching into unrelated activity is positively associated with economic complexity and human capital, both lower in developing countries (see Pinheiro et al., 2018, using export data).

Measures of technological relatedness have been constructed using patent data (e.g. Rigby, 2015; Balland and Rigby, 2017),³ and have been correlated to two outcomes: i) the *entry* of a technology in a region, measured as the first year when either a region develops relative technological advantage in a technological class (Balland et al., 2019; Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014) or a green company applies for a patent (Corradini, 2019); ii) its *intensity* measured by the *amount* of innovation that takes place (usually measured by the number of patents)⁴.

Most of the papers in the technological relatedness literature have focused on the regional level (see e.g. Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014; Balland et al., 2019; Corradini, 2019; Montesor and Quatraro, 2019; Van den Berge et al., 2020; Pinheiro et al., 2022; Barbieri et al., 2023), whereas papers at the country level are scarce. This is because regional-level analysis generally gives a more fine-grained picture. However, country-level analyses are helpful when regional-level data is not available (mostly for non-EU and US contexts) and when cross-country comparisons are of interest. Two important country-level studies are Petralia et al. (2017) and Perruchas et al. (2020). Petralia et al. (2017) focus on: i) general technologies for the years 1993–2007 and ii) specialisation/diversification. They find that technological relatedness density matters for both specialisation and diversification at the country level, for a set of 65 countries, 40 % of which are low-middle income. The effect is stronger for low-middle-income countries. Perruchas et al. (2020) use the same methodology data on 63 countries in the period 1971–2012 to study determinants of countries' diversification and specialisation for a *green* technology space only. They find that specialisation and diversification in a green technological class is more likely if related to a country's *green* knowledge base.

Different from both papers, our analysis focuses on technological entry and the intensity of innovation rather than specialization or diversification and includes more recent data covering the years 2005–2018. Additionally, Petralia et al. (2017) use USPTO data, which, in cross-country studies, may induce home-bias-effects in patenting, yielding a skewed picture of global patenting activity for countries. Instead, we use PATSTAT, which includes worldwide patents rather than US applications only (similar to Perruchas et al., 2020). In addition, while Perruchas et al. (2020) limit their analysis to green technologies and measure the relatedness of green technologies to a country's *green* knowledge base, we are interested in how countries, even those not yet very active in green patenting, can use their existing knowledge base to move towards green entry and greater intensity in CCMT innovation. Therefore, we do not require countries to have a substantial number of green patents to start with and we are thus able to have a much larger sample of 197 countries.

While not the focus of this paper, our analysis is related to the literature on technology transfer and diffusion, which studies North-South diffusion of technologies (Folmer et al., 2001; Haščić and Migotto, 2015; Dechezlepretre et al., 2011), or diffusion of technologies through e.g., trade and multinationals (Consoli et al., 2023; Costantini et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). However, these diffusion rates remain low. Less than a third of total CCMTs are transferred from high to medium-income countries and almost none to low-income countries (Probst et al., 2021). Furthermore, diffused technologies often remain either unused or yield lower benefits in terms of climate change mitigation to receiving countries than they do in creator countries (Ormrod, 1990; Aubert, 2005). Differently from this literature, we investigate how developing countries can contribute to innovation directly and to innovation tailored to their knowledge base, rather than implementing innovation from developed countries. This is relevant because innovation is more effective in driving technological development when it is tailored to the specific context. This may be achieved by better protection of intellectual property rights (IPR), at least for low levels of IPRs (see Chen and Puttitanun, 2005, who find a U-shaped relationship between IPRs and economic development using USPTO patent data).

Fig. 1 highlights the focus and motivation of our research. While we focus on CCMT innovation related to a country's knowledge

³ In these studies, technological relatedness has been defined as the number of citations between two patents that fall into different technological classes (see Rigby, 2015, for US cities) or the number of co-occurrences of two technological classes on a single patent (see Balland et al., 2019, for EU regions).

⁴ We follow Pinheiro et al. (2022), who use the term *intensity* to indicate the number of patents. Alternatively, Van den Berge and Weterings (2014) use the term *success*. This term is less appropriate for our paper because we do not measure whether an innovation will be applied and diffused in the economy. We thank an anonymous reviewer for this comment.

Fig. 1. Theoretical framework.

Continuous lines represent those mechanisms related to our research, while dotted lines represent the channels we do not focus on.

base, we show that there are also other modes of CCMT acquisition for developing countries, in particular technological transfer.⁵ Our motivation to focus on CCMT innovation related to a country's knowledge base instead of technological transfer is (1) the additional benefit own technology development can have for developing countries on economic growth in contrast to technological transfer where the main beneficiaries are the transferring parties (Romer, 1992); (2) the ease and extent which own CCMT development can be adopted, while technological transfer often requires prior knowledge acquisition and adaptation to local conditions. We also do not focus on technological transfer nor on unrelated CCMT innovations. However, they are non-trivial modes of technology acquisition and often complementary to related CCMT innovation. Finally, our paper also does not analyse the impact of innovation on economic and environmental benefits, which has been treated in separate literature (Aghion et al., 1998; Bilbao-Osorio and Rodriguez-Pose, 2004; Ulku, 2004; Aghion et al., 2009a; Hasna et al., 2023).

3. Describing innovation and technological relatedness

Technological relatedness indicates the degree to which two technological classes share similarities or complementarities in innovative output. Therefore, it captures how easily a country can move innovative output from one technological class to another. Technological relatedness builds on regional diversification theory that measures *product relatedness* using data on exports. It is based on the idea that existing local capabilities guide the direction of economic branching and related diversification into new activities: firms (countries) are more likely to enter activities related to their current product basket (see Hidalgo et al., 2007; Neffke et al., 2011, for, respectively the country and the regional level using export data of countries). This happens because relatedness induces effective knowledge transfer and recombination of existing local capabilities (Frenken et al., 2007). The same mechanisms are at play concerning technologies and the process of innovation. This is because technologies are inputs into products and hence related products often share similar or related sets of production inputs. Thus, whereas Hidalgo et al. (2007) and Neffke et al. (2011) approach focuses on activities and the product basket, our approach focuses on innovation and technology.

For our analysis, we build the *technology space*, a one-mode network representing a matrix, whose entries indicate technological relatedness between two technological classes.

Technology space We measure technological relatedness ϕ_{ij} between technological classes i and j . ϕ_{ij} captures if two

⁵ Additionally, the development of innovations that are more unrelated to the knowledge base can be linked to radical or breakthrough innovations (Castaldi et al., 2015). We do not focus on unrelated innovations, which have the potential of more radical impacts on emissions and climate change, as they are often more risky projects with high financial and human capital requirements. These innovations follow a more uncoordinated process, difficult to direct limited resources to.

technological classes i and j co-occur more often than expected. The measure is computed as follows (see also (1)):

1. We compute the number of co-occurrences o_{ij} of two technological classes on a single patent (see also Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014).
2. We normalise the number for a probabilistic similarity measure known as the association strength $s_i * s_j$, where s_i and s_j are the total numbers of patents in the technological classes i and j (Van Eck and Waltman, 2009).
3. We weight the measure by the number of patents p in the analysis.

$$\phi_{ij} = \frac{o_{ij}}{s_i * s_j} * p = \frac{\text{observed}}{\text{expected}} \quad (1)$$

Next, we test if the technological relatedness measure is larger than one, $\phi_{i,j} > 1$, using a binomial test with 95 % confidence (Neffke and Henning, 2013).⁶ We keep just entries with statistically significant $\phi_{i,j} > 1$ and we store them in a co-occurrence matrix called *technology space*. All other entries as well as the diagonal are set to zero.

The technology space is visualised as a network representation in Fig. 2 using an efficient force-directed graph drawing algorithm by Hu (2005) implemented in Gephi 0.9.6 based on an attraction-repulsion model. The network visualisation can be found as an interactive network following instructions in Appendix A.11.⁷ In this technology space, technological classes are located near each other depending on their relative degree of relatedness. This leads to the clustering of technological classes belonging to the same family. Technological classes occupy the centre of the technology space if they are related to many other technological classes. Compared to peripheral classes, central classes are relatively more complex and have a higher probability to innovate by combining a diverse set of technologies.⁸

We aggregate the 169 technological classes into nine sub-classes A: Human necessities (red), B: Performing operations; transporting (orange), C: Chemistry; metallurgy (light blue), D: Textiles; paper (dark green), E: Fixed constructions (brown), F: Mechanical engineering; lightning; heating; weapons; blasting engines or pumps (yellow), G: Physics (dark blue), H: Electricity (grey) and Y: CCMTs (light green). The 44 CCMT classes (light green) cluster in the top left and are close to technologies of sub-class F. This reflects high relatedness between Y- and F-technologies and the strong potential to innovate CCMTs if knowledge in F-classes is high. As an example, the black box in Fig. 2 focuses on the technological class F25.⁹ The ego-network of class F25 shows that it is related to 10 CCMTs. Therefore, diversification from F25 towards CCMTs is likely to be more promising than diversifying from technological classes further away from the CCMT cluster.

Very distant classes from the CCMT cluster are for example human necessities (A; red), and textiles and paper (D; dark green), while CCMTs for more efficient production, processes (Y02P) and waste management (Y02W) are closely related to technologies in chemistry and metallurgy (C; light blue). Fixed construction (E; brown) and many electricity classes (H; grey) are close to each other in the technology space and surround CCMTs in housing, house appliances or related end-user applications (Y02B). This happens because construction is one of the most energy and emission-intensive industries (Chen et al., 2023). Very few patents in the Y02-classes related to ICT exist (Y02D), and thus they are at the periphery (top-right) of the technology space. Damioli et al. (2024) show, that while patenting in digital technologies took off around 2005, digital-green patents saw a stark increase around 5 years later.

To describe the evolution of green patents in ICTs encompassing digital technologies, we also construct the technology space considering different time frames. Fig. 3 presents the oldest (1996–2001) and most recent (2016–2020) five-year technology spaces. It shows that, while Y02D classes became closer connected to the main component of the network over time, adjustments of CPC-classes within the network are minor, indicating slow changing relatedness between technological classes and a high persistence over time. In both networks, Y02D classes are strongly related with information storage technologies (e.g., G11, highlighted), an area with an increasing need for environmental innovations considering its emissions already exceed those from the airline industry (Gonzalez Monserrate, 2022). However, due to still low patenting and the short time frames considered in the construction of the technology space, the Y02D50 class fails to achieve a significant co-occurrence with other technological classes and hence remains isolated and disconnected from the main component.

Relatedness density Our main independent variable, the Relatedness density is constructed as follows:

1. We create a measure of *relative technological advantage (RTA)* of a country c in a technological class i in year t . RTA is greater than one if a country has a greater fraction of patent applications in a specific technological class than the global reference group

⁶ Expected co-occurrence assumes that the co-occurrence of two technological classes is statistically independent of each other (Van Eck and Waltman, 2009).

⁷ Hoovering with the cursor over technological classes displays the ego-network, highlighting those CPC-classes related to the selected technological class. Information on network measures (e.g. node centrality, node degree, etc.) for each technological class can be found by clicking on a CPC-class.

⁸ Another explanation for technologies occupying the periphery besides low complexity could be a low number of patents. Examining the evolution of the network can help identify whether low patenting is due to the emergence or decline of a technological class (see Fig. 3 for the emergence of Y02D classes).

⁹ Technological class F25 contains technologies that fall into the category of Refrigeration or Cooling; Combined Heating and Refrigeration Systems; Heat Pump Systems; Manufacturer Storage of Ice; Liquefaction Solidification of Gases.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the Technology Space.

Technology spaces constructed using patents over the time period 1996–2001 (left) and over the time period 2016–2020 (right) (Visualisation of the network using the Fruchterman-Reingold force-directed algorithm in R from the *igraph*-package).

simultaneously has *RTA*. The technological relatedness of this subset of classes is then summed up and compared to the maximum technological relatedness of i to all other classes.

4. Empirical framework

4.1. Data

To measure innovation and technological relatedness, we use patent data (see also Griliches, 1990; Johnstone et al., 2010), specifically the Autumn Edition 2020 of the Database *PATSTAT* from the European Patent Office (EPO) covering worldwide patent applications. To identify technological classes, we use the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) scheme. Thanks to the recent addition of the Y02 classes by the EPO, identification of CCMTs is now possible.

To identify CCMTs, we use a 6-digit classification level, and we focus on ‘technologies or applications for mitigation or adaptation against climate change’, labelled with the three-digit prefix *Y02*. They include the “Technologies for the adaptation to adverse effects of climate change on human, industrial or economic activities” (*Y02A*) and “Technologies for the mitigation against climate change” within the themes of buildings (*Y02B*), GHG capture (*Y02C*), ICTs (*Y02D*), energy (*Y02E*), industry, transport and waste and wastewater management (*Y02W*) (USPTO, 2021; Angelucci et al., 2018). All other technological classes are classified on a 3-digit level. Within the *Y02*-class, CCMTs are categorised into 44 sub-classes (see Appendix A.1).

We use data over the years 2000–2018. We do not consider the years 2019 and 2020 due to incomplete data recording. Years 2000–2004 are used to compute a 5-year moving average of *Relatedness Density* with one-year lag. Therefore, the first year used in the analysis is 2005. We drop 35 countries because they did not apply for any CCMT patents during 2000–2018.¹⁰ This selection results in 197 countries classified according to the 2020 WESP or LDC reports (UN, 2020; UNCTAD, 2020) into developed countries (22.8 %) and developing countries (77.2 %).¹¹ A list of countries used can be found in Appendix A.3.

Patents can be filed at different patent offices. To avoid double counting of applications with the same technical content, we select one application only for each DOCDB family.¹² A list of the number of patents selected from each patent office is included in Appendix A.4. Henceforth, we refer to the selected application from a DOCDB family simply as “patent”. We opted not to focus on granted patents which include high-quality innovations. Instead, we focused on applications because using granted patents would limit our analysis to a shorter time frame, given that the patent examination process can span several years from the initial filing to the grant date.¹³

In line with the literature, (see e.g., Petralia et al., 2017; Balland et al., 2019; Barbieri et al., 2023), we believe using inventors over

¹⁰ Countries that did not apply for any CCMT patents during 2000–2018 are: Angola, Saint Barthelemy, Cook Islands, Curacao, French Guiana, Guernsey, Greenland, South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands, Guam, British Indian Ocean Territory, Kiribati, Comoros, Saint Lucia, Marshall Islands, Northern Mariana Islands, Martinique, Mozambique, Norfolk Island, Nauru, Papua New Guinea, Saint Pierre and Miquelon, Pitcairn, Palau, Solomon Islands, Ascension and Tristan da Cunha Saint Helena, Svalbard and Jan Mayen, Suriname, South Sudan, Sint Maarten (Dutch part), Chad, US Minor Outlying Islands, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Vanuatu, Wallis and Futuna.

¹¹ We classify economies in transition and economies not listed in the two UN reports into either developed or developing countries depending on whether GDP per capita is closer to the median value of GDP per capita in developed or developing countries.

¹² We select the application within a DOCDB family which has the largest number of inventors. This choice permits us to represent best everyone involved in the innovation process. If two applications have the same number of inventors, we select the one with the largest number of applicants and then the publication with the earliest application date.

¹³ See <https://www.epo.org/en/about-us/services-and-activities/quality/statistics/examination> for examination length at the EPO, with mean of 24.3 months up to 100 months lag between filing and granting.

applicants better captures where knowledge is located, for three reasons. First, due to multinational activities spanning across countries, focusing on applicants might only reflect the biggest organization participating in the patenting process, which may not align with the actual place where the knowledge originated and was applied. For example, the headquarters in a developed country could file a patent developed by a subsidiary in a developing one, and thus be listed as the applicant, while the inventor from the subsidiary would be listed as the inventor. These cases of domestic ownership of foreign inventions are common in cross-border patents. Second, when innovation is collaborative and involves different entities, it can happen that only one party is listed as an applicant, while all collaborative parties are listed as inventors. These types of cross-border patents are the second most common (OECD, 2009). Last, while patents lay open the knowledge encapsulated in an invention, inventors can share the knowledge with their networks or diffuse it to other fields via labour mobility.

Using patent (count) data has advantages and drawbacks (see Griliches, 1990; OECD, 2009, for further discussion on the use of patent data). A main advantage is the ability to locate innovation in time and space because patent data includes the inventors' address and information on dates of application (Tanner, 2011). However, not all innovations are patented or are patented by a limited number of institutions. Reasons for this can be strategic, to not reveal the innovation to competitors, but also financial, as filing a patent can be costly. The latter might result, especially in developing countries, in lower propensity to patent.

Another limitation of patent count data is that it does not permit to place an economic value on innovation nor directly allows to measure its environmental impact. Besides this, an innovation may never reach the market because firms may decide to file for a patent for purely strategic reasons (e.g. to block competitors' development of certain technologies). This implies, that while patent data may give information on the technological knowledge, it (1) cannot capture other non-technological factors important for understanding the usefulness and value of a patented invention, and (2) does not provide a complete picture of all knowledge present in a country and therefore provides a skewed picture of the knowledge base of a country. Despite its drawbacks, patent data is used widely in cross-country analyses of innovation activities and is the only proxy for innovation that allows us to analyse technological relatedness and countries' knowledge bases on a close-to-global level.

We construct technological relatedness ϕ_{ij} defined in (1) using patents over the years 1996–2020,¹⁴ assuming static technological relatedness for this period and across space (e.g. Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014; Corradini, 2019; Balland et al., 2019). This assumption is motivated by high correlations of co-occurrence measures across time (see Boschma et al. (2014) and our analysis of the evolution of the technology space in Fig. 3). This leads to a total number of 17,094,470 patents over the years 1996–2020.¹⁵ The relatedness measure for each pair of technological classes results in a co-occurrence matrix with dimensions 169×169 visualised in network form as the technology space in Fig. 2. 13.3 % of all possible links are present, meaning that 13.3 % of the pairs of technological classes are related according to (1).

4.2. Empirical specification and descriptive statistics

We proxy the innovation $Intensity_{i,c,t}$ of a CCMT (i) per country (c) and year (t) with the number of patent applications for that CCMT class (44 classes), per country (197 countries) and per year (14 years), resulting in 121,352 observations. To locate innovations, we use the country of residence of the inventors and the earliest filing year recorded for a patent application. If multiple inventors are part of a single patent application, each inventor counts to one unit (see Tanner, 2011). If no inventor is listed, we consider the applicant. This only happens in around 2 % of the cases. In our sample, developed countries have on average slightly fewer inventors listed on a patent than developing countries (2.44 vs 2.54 respectively), whereas the average number of applicants per patent is higher in developed countries (1.99 vs 1.56) hinting at more collaborative rather than hierarchical co-inventions in the former. Indeed, while the number of cross-border patents is around 5 % in our sample,¹⁶ 60 % of this cross-border collaboration is among developed countries, 34 % involves inventors from developed and developing countries and only the remaining 6 % is among developing countries.

The main independent variable of interest ($Relatedness\ density_{i,c,t-1}$) measures the *degree of relatedness* between a CCMT and a country's knowledge base and it is constructed as explained in Section 3. Due to large fluctuations in this variable over time, we use a 5-year rolling mean (see also Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014). In Eq. (1), we estimate the following relationship, to test hypotheses H1 and H2:

$$Intensity_{i,c,t} = \beta_1 \times Relatedness\ density_{i,c,t-1} + \mathbf{x}^T \gamma + \rho_c + \tau_i + \alpha_t + e_{i,c,t} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where \mathbf{x} is a set of controls for time-varying effects at the country and technology levels. It includes (1) *cumulative count of total patents developed in a country*, to control for differences across countries and time in overall patenting activity, discounted by 20 % annually,¹⁷ (2) *cumulative count of patents in each CCMT class*, discounted at a 20 % annual rate, to control for changes over time in the size of a technological class; (3) *growth rate of patenting activity on the technology level*, to control for up- or downswings of patenting activity within a technological class over time. All independent variables are lagged by one year because country characteristics precede

¹⁴ We use DOCDB family IDs' first filing between 1996–2020.

¹⁵ As a robustness check, we also present in the Appendix A.8 an econometric analysis based on technological relatedness computed for two overlapping periods 1996–2010 and 2006–2020.

¹⁶ Cross-border patents are defined here as applications with inventors from at least two different countries.

¹⁷ We discount the patent to reflect knowledge depreciation over time. Griliches (1990) estimates the returns of patents to depreciate between 10% to 20% annually. Literature commonly uses a 20% depreciation rate (e.g. Zucker et al., 2007; Van den Berge and Weterings, 2014).

emerging innovation. Cumulative patent counts on country and technology levels are log-transformed.

Descriptive statistics of these variables are presented in the top panel of [Table 1](#). There are significant differences in the growth rates of CCMT classes. The largest increase in patents was observed for the CCMT class Y02E60 with 444,967 additional patents over 2005–2018. In terms of average annual growth rates, faster growing CCMT classes over this period have been Y02T90 (transportation enabling technologies) and Y02E70 (energy conversion or management systems reducing GHG emissions). CCMT classes Y02D50 and Y02D70 have received the fewest number of additional patents.

[Fig. 4](#) shows that patenting activity in general (panel a) and patenting activity in CCMTs (panel b) are significantly lower in developing countries. This translates to a lower potential for developing countries to gain RTA in a technological class ([Fig. 4](#), panel c), which results in lower relatedness densities with CCMTs. This means that in general developed countries' knowledge base is more likely to be related to a CCMT class and is on average more strongly related to a CCMT class than the knowledge base of developing countries ([Fig. 4](#), panel d).

The left panel of [Fig. 5](#) shows that, especially for patent applications in CCMTs, developing countries slowly catch up with developed countries, suggesting convergence between the two groups from 2012 onwards. Convergence is partially driven by the decline of CCMT patenting by developed countries around 2011. Despite this decline, the right panel of [Fig. 5](#) shows that countries' knowledge bases increased in relatedness with CCMTs, both for developed and developing countries.

Both the relatedness to CCMTs and the number of RTAs that countries already hold in CCMTs increase over time. This is shown in [Fig. 6](#), where the left panel indicates the total number of RTAs developing versus developed countries hold in Y02-classes and the right panel the percentage of RTAs held in CCMTs. On average, developing countries held RTAs in around 17.5 % of the 44 CCMT classes in 2018 (32.5 % for developed). This is an improvement of nearly 10 % with respect to 2005 level (similar for developed countries), indicating the increasing importance of innovation in CCMTs.

The evolution of the knowledge bases for developed and developing countries is visualised in [Appendix Figure F2](#). It shows two-mode networks of countries being connected to technological classes based on their RTAs for the years 2008 and 2018. Firstly, we observe an increasing incorporation of CCMTs into the networks due to the increasing number of RTAs in CCMTs. Secondly, overall network densities increase for developed countries by 1.2 % (to an overall density of 11.7 %) and for developing countries by 2.5 % (to an overall density of 7.9 %) showing slight convergence in terms of complexity of the two country groups' knowledge bases.

These findings imply that (1) developing countries are already improving their role in the development of CCMTs by increasing their breadth of competitive advantages in CCMTs and (2) overall knowledge bases in developing countries become more complex with slight convergence to developed countries, making the development of complex CCMTs more probable.

[Table 2](#) shows a ranking of the top 10 innovators in all technological classes and in CCMT classes. China, South Korea, Taiwan and Russia are the countries in this list classified as developing. When controlling for quality patents by only making use of patents with a DOCDB family size greater than one, as done in [Appendix A.7](#) (see [Table T8](#)), Russia drops out of the ranking and is replaced by Italy. China also loses many insignificant patents, especially in CCMTs. The ranking according to all technological classes and the one for CCMT classes have minor differences, indicating that not only general but also CCMT innovations are highly concentrated in a few countries.

To test if human capital, R&D expenditure, and more stringent environmental policies affect CCMT innovations (hypotheses H3, H4, and H5), we estimate [Eq. \(2\)](#) which, relative to [Eq. \(1\)](#) also includes tertiary education, R&D expenditure and an index for environmental policy stringency, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Intensity_{i,c,t} = & \beta_1 \times Relatedness\ density_{i,c,t-1} + \beta_2 \times Education_{c,t-1} + \beta_3 \times R\&D\ expenditure_{c,t-1} + \beta_4 \times EPS_{c,t-1} + x^T \gamma + \rho_c + \tau_i + \alpha_t \\ & + \epsilon_{i,c,t} \end{aligned} \quad (Eq. 2)$$

When estimating [Eq. \(2\)](#), we do not control for patenting activity (i.e. the total number of patent applications of a country in a year) due to multicollinearity with R&D expenditure.¹⁸ To measure *human capital*, we use the lagged number of people enrolled in tertiary education (both sexes), using the World Bank data on Education Statistics. To measure *financial support* to innovation, we use the lagged gross domestic R&D expenditure as a percentage of GDP (see [Aron and Bell, 2010](#)), using data from the World Development Indicators provided by the World Bank. To measure *EPS*, we create an index using information from the International Environmental Agreements Database (IEADB) and the United Nations Treaty Collection (UNTC) for 13 international environmental agreements (see [Appendix A.6](#) for a list of agreements included). Each point of the index corresponds to an additional agreement entered into force ([Lanjouw and Mody, 1993](#)). The index ranges from 0 to 13 and is lagged by one year. Incomplete data recording on mainly R&D expenditure reduces the country sample from 197 to 67 countries, out of which 57 % are developing countries and 43 % developed countries (see [Appendix A.3](#)).¹⁹

Descriptive statistics of these variables and the controls are presented in the bottom panel of [Table 1](#). Due to mainly missing data

¹⁸ Correlation between these two variables is 70%. Not controlling for total patenting activity is not an issue here, as the main objective is to test whether human capital, financial support and incentive constraints hamper the development of innovation. Any omitted effect due to the exclusion of patenting activity that could influence the coefficients on human capital or EPS should be partially picked up by R&D expenditure.

¹⁹ Countries with missing data for more than half of the years in any variable are dropped and occasional missing values in the rest of the sample are imputed using linear interpolation. For missing values in the first or last year of data recording, the first and last year of available data respectively is used.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics.

Statistics of *Relatedness density*_{*c,t-1*} are based on 5-year rolling mean; Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) are based on log-transformed variables of *Patenting activity*_{*c,t-1*} and *Y02 patenting*_{*i,t-1*}.

Based on data used for estimating Eq. (1) (197 countries)						
Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max	VIF
Intensity _{<i>i,c,t</i>}	121,352	19.389	228.341	0	14,537	
Rel. Density _{<i>i,c,t-1</i>}	121,352	6.778	17.806	0	100	1.221
Patenting activity _{<i>c,t-1</i>}	121,352	25,161.4	140,473.5	0	1706,670.0	1.200
Y02 patenting _{<i>i,t-1</i>}	121,352	14,094.1	24,878.9	0.3	172,738.1	1.037
Tech. Growth _{<i>i,t-1</i>} (%)	121,352	8.894	13.638	-25.000	97.700	1.022
Based on data used for Eq. (2) (67 countries)						
Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max	VIF
Intensity _{<i>i,c,t</i>}	41,272	23.865	214.675	0	9247	
Rel. Density _{<i>i,c,t-1</i>}	41,272	12.734	23.120	0.000	100.000	1.101
Education _{<i>c,t-1</i>}	41,272	1652,470	4968,168	2692	44,127,509	1.062
R&D expenditure _{<i>c,t-1</i>}	41,272	0.990	0.945	0.015	4.816	1.236
EPS _{<i>c,t-1</i>}	41,272	9.844	1.796	0	13	1.277
Tech. Growth _{<i>i,t-1</i>} (%)	41,272	8.894	13.639	-25.000	97.700	1.036
Y02 patenting _{<i>i,t-1</i>}	41,272	14,094.1	24,879.1	0.3	172,738.1	1.057

Fig. 4. Boxplots aggregated by countries development status over the years 2005- 2018.

Based on data sample used for estimating Eq. (1); from left to right: (a) Number of patent applications (per 1000 inhabitants, per year) for countries that had at least one patent application in each year - axis log-transformed, (b) Number of CCMT patent applications (per 1000 inhabitants, per year) for countries that had at least one CCMT patent application in each year - axis log-transformed, (c) Number of technological classes a country has RTA in, and (d) Relatedness of CCMTs to a countries knowledge base given that relatedness is not zero - axis log-transformed.

from developing countries, average values for *Intensity*_{*i,c,t*} and *Relatedness density*_{*i,c,t-1*} are higher with respect to the full dataset. The technology-level variables *Y02 patenting* and *Technology growth* remain unchanged. Fig. 7 shows the distribution of education (as % of the population), R&D expenditure and stringency of environmental policy, by development status of countries in the sample. As expected, all three variables are significantly higher in developed countries.

We estimate Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) using a generalised linear model (GLM), with country (ρ_c), time (α_t) and technological class (τ_i) fixed effects due to our positively-bounded dependent variable. The dependent variable *Intensity*_{*i,c,t*} is a discrete, non-negative count variable, with a large proportion of zeros as the distribution in Fig. 8 shows. The zeros stem from two sources: 1) Sampling zeros: a country takes part in innovative activity in a CCMT class but fails in some years to generate innovative output (patents), yielding occasional zeros throughout the sample period and 2) Structural zeros: a country does not take part in innovative activity in a CCMT class throughout the sample period, resulting in always zeros (Thomas et al., 2018).

To take structural zeros into account, we estimate a zero-inflated negative binomial model (ZINB), a count model where the zero is inflated. We estimate the probability of reporting a zero (*selection equation*) via logit (Pedace, 2013). This is the probability of country *c* not achieving technological *entry* in a technology *i*. To estimate the *Intensity* with the count model (i.e. the number of patents developed

Fig. 5. *Left panel:* Total number of patents for developed (dark green) and developing (yellow) countries; dotted lines showing the total number of CCMT patent applications; *Right panel:* Five-year rolling mean of relatedness density of CCMTs to countries' knowledge bases in % (within-year means for developed and developing countries) with dotted lines showing relatedness density without rolling means. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. *Left panel:* Total number of CCMT classes in which a relative technological advantage is held; grouped by developed and developing countries; Total count is the sum within these groups; *Right panel:* Percentage of CCMT classes in which RTAs are held; grouped by developed and developing countries.

Binary RTA is used; calculated using the patent stock build with cumulative count of patents from 2000 onwards with 20 %-annual depreciation.

Table 2

Top 10 countries in patenting and CCMT patenting.

Based on patent applications over the years 2005–2018; Total patents: sum of the number of patents in each technological class; CCMT patents: sum of the number of patents in each CCMT class.

Rank	Country	Total Patents	Country	CCMT Patents
1	United States	209,361,504	Republic of Korea	534,741
2	Republic of Korea	138,338,068	United States	467,604
3	Japan	109,533,776	Japan	348,307
4	Germany	80,568,840	Germany	249,732
5	China	55,995,720	China	226,910
6	Taiwan	24,512,004	France	74,004
7	France	23,065,416	Taiwan	71,422
8	United Kingdom	15,218,412	Russia	51,654
9	Russia	12,931,512	United Kingdom	38,556
10	Canada	11,706,816	Canada	28,303

in a CCMT class), assuming a non-zero regime is selected, we use a negative binomial mode to account for overdispersion, because the variance of $Intensity_{i,c,t}$ is much greater than the mean as we can see from Table 1 (Verbeek, 2017). The count model estimates the $Intensity$ of technology i in country c for technologies that have entered a country. Standard errors are clustered at the country level.

We include the same control variables in the count and the selection parts of the model for several reasons: (1) overall patenting activity reflects a country's structural ability to patent or not as well as, if a country has the potential, the amount of it, (2) propensity to patent in specific technological domains differs, potentially causing structurally no patenting in certain domains (e.g. due to nascent or

Fig. 7. Boxplots aggregated by countries development status over the years 2005- 2018
 From left to right: (a) enrolment in tertiary education (in % of population) ^a, (b) R&D expenditure (in % of GDP) ^b and (c) Environmental Policy Stringency (index from 0 to 13) ^c.

^aCountries from full sample **not** included in this statistic: AF, AG, AI, AS, AU, BB, BO, BS, CD, CF, CG, CI, DE, DM, DO, EC, ER, FJ, FO, GA, GD, GI, GM, GP, GQ, GT, HT, IM, IQ, JE, KE, KN, KP, KY, LR, LY, MC, MM, MS, MV, NC, NG, NI, NZ, PE, PF, PS, RE, SC, SG, SL, SM, SO, ST, SZ, TC, TK, TM, TO, TT, TV, TW, US, VA, VE, VG, VI, WS, ZA, ZM, ZW ^b Countries from full sample **not** included in this statistic: AD, AE, AF, AG, AI, AL, AS, AU, AW, BB, BD, BF, BH, BI, BJ, BM, BN, BO, BS, BT, BW, BZ, CD, CF, CG, CH, CI, CM, CV, DJ, DM, DO, DZ, ER, ET, FJ, FO, GA, GD, GH, GI, GM, GN, GP, GQ, GY, HN, HT, ID, IM, IQ, JE, JM, JO, KE, KH, KN, KP, KY, LA, LB, LI, LK, LR, LS, LY, MA, MC, ML, MM, MR, MS, MU, MV, MW, NC, NE, NG, NI, NP, NZ, OM, PF, pH PK, PR, PS, QA, RE, RW, SC, SD, SL, SM, SN, SO, ST, SY, SZ, TC, TG, TK, TM, TO, TV, TW, TZ, UG, VA, VE, VG, VI, VN, WS, YE, ZM, ZW ^c Countries from full sample **not** included in this statistic: AI, AS, AW, BM, FO, GI, GP, HK, IM, JE, KY, MO, NC, PF, PR, RE, TC, TK, TW, VA, VI

Fig. 8. Over-dispersion of $Intensity_{i,c,t}$.
 Distribution of the dependent variable displaying over-dispersion; Based on data sample used estimation of Eq. (1).

dying technological fields), but also determines the amount of patenting in others, due to general differences in propensity to patent, (3) negative technological growth in emerging technologies could not only result in a lower count of patents but also for some fields to structural zeros if the field is becoming obsolete in terms of new technological additions (vice versa for emerging technologies).

4.3. Results

Table 3 shows the estimated coefficients of Eq. (1). Model 1 and Model 2 include all 197 countries, while Model 3 only includes developing countries and Model 4 only developed countries. For the selection equation, we expect relatedness density to negatively affect the probability of producing zero patents. The opposite is true in the count model part. The coefficients of all the controls (total

Table 3
Results of estimating Eq. (1) using ZINB: $Intensity_{i,c,t}$ as dependent variable
Robust clustered standard errors on country level in parentheses.

	Model (1) full sample	Model (2) full sample	Model (3) developing	Model (4) developed
Count n				
(Intercept)	-4.268** (0.213)	-8.549*** (0.528)	-8.371*** (1.254)	-9.115*** (0.697)
Relatedness density $_{i,c,t-1}$ (in %)	0.015** (0.001)	0.015*** (0.001)	0.015*** (0.002)	0.014*** (0.001)
Technology growth $_{i,t-1}$ (in %)		0.017** (0.002)	0.013*** (0.003)	0.019*** (0.003)
ln(Patenting activity $_{c,t-1}$)		0.345** (0.142)	0.472** (0.185)	0.292* (0.167)
ln(Y02 patenting $_{i,t-1}$)		0.476*** (0.058)	0.494*** (0.111)	0.492*** (0.061)
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Y02 FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Inflate (logit)				
(Intercept)	9.514*** (1.469)	6.508*** (1.413)	5.389*** (1.905)	5.378** (2.251)
Relatedness density $_{i,c,t-1}$ (in %)	-0.015*** (0.002)	-0.015*** (0.002)	-0.016*** (0.003)	-0.014*** (0.004)
Technology growth $_{i,t-1}$ (in %)	-0.022** (0.005)	-0.011*** (0.004)	-0.016*** (0.006)	-0.008* (0.005)
ln(Patenting activity $_{c,t-1}$)	-0.852*** (0.112)	-0.603*** (0.114)	-0.557*** (0.135)	-0.461 (0.291)
ln(Y02 patenting $_{i,t-1}$)	-0.496** (0.146)	-0.178 (0.139)	-0.247 (0.213)	-0.098 (0.218)
Over-disp. Parameter				
log(theta)	0.4622 (0.013)	0.4899 (0.0128)	0.2297 (0.021)	0.7826 (0.017)
No. obs	121,352	121,352	93,632	27,720
Log-likelihood	-99,093	-98,867	-43,893	-54,235
AIC	199,209.8	198,764.4	88,635.8	108,891.1

Note:

* $p < 0.1$;

** $p < 0.05$;

*** $p < 0.01$.

patenting activity, patent activity in CCMT classes and technological growth) are also expected to be positive in the count part and negative in the regime selection one.

Consider first the selection equation in Table 3 (bottom panel). Model 2 shows that a one standard deviation increase (equivalent to an increase of 17.806 %) in relatedness density decreases the probability of always reporting a zero by 76.6 %.²⁰ The negative coefficient of relatedness density for developing countries (Model 3) is smaller than the coefficient for the sample of developed countries (Model 4). A 1 % increase in relatedness density decreases the probability of always reporting a zero by 5.74 % for developing and 2.9 % for developed countries. The effect size is therefore close to double for the former group and suggests that relatedness density has a more crucial role at early stages of development.²¹

In all specifications technological growth in a Y02-class is associated with a lower probability of always being in the zero group, indicating that expanding technological fields can spur the innovation entry of a country into this field. The negative coefficient on patenting activity is primarily driven by developing countries, suggesting that some developing countries indeed face a structural constraint in their overall ability to patent. This indicates that, for developing countries, it matters if patenting is a common practice or not. This is not the case for developed countries.

Consider now the count part in Table 3 (top panel). Higher relatedness density is associated with more innovations in a CCMT-class. A one-unit increase in relatedness density, i.e., relatedness of a CCMT-class to a country's knowledge base increases by 1 %, results in a $e^{0.015} = 1.0151$ fold increase in the expected number of the given CCMT to be patented. Control variables show that: (1) the more active a country is in patenting, (2) the bigger the size of a CCMT-class, and (3) the higher the growth rate of a CCMT-class, the higher

²⁰ This is derived from the odds ratio computed as $e^{\beta \times \delta}$ (where β is the estimated coefficient and δ the standard deviation of the measured variable). The odds ratio for *Relatedness Density* in Model 2 would therefore be $e^{0.015 \times 17.806} = 0.76560$.

²¹ Despite the effect size being close to double it is difficult to test whether the difference of the two coefficients is statistically significant in a mixture model. In our case, this challenge is augmented by using fixed effects and multiple controls. Besides this, convergence is difficult to achieve in a model that would include an interaction term indicating the development status.

the expected number of patent applications in a CCMT-class.

All in all, our results support hypothesis H1 and suggest that relatedness density affects CCMT innovation, decreasing both the probability of structural zeros and its volume. Therefore, relatedness density can be used to guide countries through more targeted R&D expenditure towards technological entry and innovation intensities of CCMTs.

The comparison between Model 3 and Model 4 provides evidence of the validity of hypothesis H2. Developing countries rely more on technological relatedness of innovation than developed ones. In developing countries, a 1 % increase in relatedness density is estimated to result in a 1.0151 fold increase in the expected number of patent applications in a CCMT-class, while for developed countries this effect is slightly lower with a 1.0141 fold increase. In addition, the selection equation for developed countries suggests that the probability of having a structural zero is very low and stable. Indeed, relatedness density is the only determinant and most of the controls are either not statistically significant or significant at the 10 % level. The results substantially hold even if we exclude the top innovators from the sample of developing countries, that is China, South Korea, Taiwan and Russia. In particular, when we exclude the top innovators the effect of relatedness on the probability to always report a zero in the selection part of the model is stronger, while the coefficient on the count part decreases, indicating that the small differences found in the main estimation between developed and developing countries in the count part is mainly driven by top innovators of developing countries. We conclude from this that relatedness is particularly important for developing countries in explaining entry into CCMTs rather than intensity of CCMTs (results are presented in [Appendix A10](#)).

[Table 4](#) shows the results of estimating [Eq. \(2\)](#), used to test hypotheses H3, H4 and H5. Most coefficients have the expected sign. In the count part, the model coefficients of relatedness density are slightly higher than those from estimating [Eq. \(1\)](#). This is due to dropping the measure of patenting activity, which would control for the general level of patent applications in a year per country. Due to a smaller sample with fewer developing countries, the average patenting used for estimating [Eq. \(2\)](#) is much higher than in the sample used for estimating [Eq. \(1\)](#). Additionally, patenting activity is positively associated with relatedness density. By omitting the variable, the coefficient of relatedness density is carrying some part of this effect through. The Akaike information criteria (AIC) indicates that including the measure of tertiary education and R&D expenditure improves the fit of the model. While the index for environmental policy stringency also slightly improves the model fit, it is not statistically significant in either the selection or the count part of the model.

In the count part of the model, we only find a statistically positive effect on innovation intensity in CCMT classes for tertiary education, supporting hypothesis H3. This finding is also robust across all estimations in our robustness checks. We do not find sufficient evidence for the effect of R&D expenditure and of environmental policy on the count of patents in a CCMT-class.

The results of the selection equation are similar to those estimated using [Eq. \(1\)](#). High relatedness density decreases the probability of reporting a zero. Tertiary education remains important and R&D expenditure now also becomes statistically significant. Using Model 7, a one standard deviation increase in the percentage of GDP spent on R&D, increases the probability of reporting a non-zero outcome by $e^{-0.523 \cdot 0.945} = 61\%$. The result provides weak evidence for hypothesis H4 as one of our robustness checks fails to show significant effects. Environmental policy stringency remains not statistically significant. This result could be partially due to: (1) little within-country variation of the variable across time, (2) the effect of environmental policies taking longer than a year, (3) the variable being an imperfect proxy of policy pressure felt in a country.

4.4. Robustness checks

In addition to the robustness check in which we analyse whether differences in the effect of relatedness density between developed and developing countries are driven by the top innovators among the developing country subsample, we perform three other robustness checks. Our first robustness check is about patent quality to investigate whether results change if we exclude low-value patents. Therefore, in [Appendix A.7](#) we restrict our analyses to patents that have a DOCDB family size greater than one, to decrease issues of counting low-value patents. The results confirm our main findings. Additionally, the difference in the magnitude of the coefficient on relatedness density between developing and developed countries (Model 3 and Model 4 estimating [Eq. \(1\)](#)) is bigger than that estimated using our main sample.

Our second robustness check is about our measure of technological relatedness. Technological relatedness is thought to be persistent and thus we have used in our main specification a measure constructed over the years 1996–2020. However, to test the robustness of our results, we estimate [Eq. \(1\)](#) using a relatedness density based on a varying technology space (for years 1996–2010 and years 2006–2020). Results can be found in the [Appendix A.8](#).

Our third robustness check is about identification in ZINB models. ZINB models are estimated by maximum likelihood and identification is achieved via functional form. Thus, we can use the same controls for both the selection equation and the count part. However, identification is facilitated by the use of an exclusion restriction, a variable that is only included in the selection equation. Therefore, we also present two robustness checks controlling for strong shocks potentially able to temporarily shut down internal innovation activities and produce structural zeros. These shocks are political factors such as political instability, war or disturbance. As exclusion restrictions, we use a one-year lag of the World Bank measure on Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism from the World Bank Worldwide Governance Indicators collection as well as a weaker measure using the World Bank measure on the Rule of Law. Results for the robustness of [Eq. \(1\)](#) and [Eq. \(2\)](#) are presented in [Appendix A.9](#) in Tables T13 and T14 respectively. These results are very similar to those in the main specifications.

Table 4Results of estimating Eq. (2) using ZINB: $Intensity_{i,c,t}$ as dependent variable

Robust clustered standard errors on country level in parentheses; all specifications with small sample of 67 countries.

	Model (5)	Model (6)	Model (7)	Model (8)
Count n				
(Intercept)	-6.934*** (0.557)	-12.725*** (3.077)	-13.174*** (2.825)	-13.655*** (2.683)
Rel. density $_{i,c,t-1}$ (in %)	0.015*** (0.001)	0.015*** (0.001)	0.015*** (0.001)	0.015*** (0.001)
ln(Education $_{c,t-1}$)		0.496* (0.274)	0.534** (0.248)	0.529** (0.249)
R&D expend. $_{c,t-1}$ (% of GDP)			-0.127 (0.203)	-0.129 (0.201)
EPS $_{c,t-1}$				0.059 (0.061)
ln(Y02 patenting $_{i,t-1}$)	0.484*** (0.079)	0.492*** (0.076)	0.494*** (0.077)	0.492*** (0.076)
Techn. growth $_{i,t-1}$ (in %)	0.017*** (0.002)	0.017*** (0.002)	0.017*** (0.002)	0.017*** (0.002)
Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Country, Year, Y02)				
Inflate (logit)				
(Intercept)	4.198** (1.865)	14.653*** (3.318)	13.244*** (2.966)	12.571*** (3.088)
Rel. density $_{i,c,t-1}$ (in %)	-0.018*** (0.003)	-0.018*** (0.003)	-0.018*** (0.003)	-0.018*** (0.003)
ln(Education $_{c,t-1}$)		-0.936*** (0.242)	-0.818*** (0.200)	-0.821*** (0.200)
R&D expend. $_{c,t-1}$ (% of GDP)			-0.523** (0.224)	-0.531** (0.226)
EPS $_{c,t-1}$				0.078 (0.053)
ln(Y02 patenting $_{i,t-1}$)	-0.201 (0.206)	-0.145 (0.216)	-0.131 (0.217)	-0.134 (0.219)
Techn. growth $_{i,t-1}$ (in %)	-0.007* (0.004)	-0.008* (0.004)	-0.008* (0.004)	-0.008* (0.004)
Over-disp. Parameter				
log(theta)	0.4377 (0.0153)	0.4434 (0.0153)	0.4435 (0.0153)	0.4447 (0.0153)
No. obs	41,272	41,272	41,272	41,272
Log-likelihood	-65,587	-65,491	-65,483	-65,478
AIC	13,310,679.9	131,492.5	131,479.6	131,475

Note:.

* $p < 0.1$;** $p < 0.05$;*** $p < 0.01$.

5. Identifying the potential of countries in CCMT- innovation

Results in Section 4.3 show that the relatedness of CCMTs to a country's knowledge base is positively correlated with CCMT innovation. These results provide an indication of the innovation potential of a country. This is particularly relevant for the economic growth that many developing countries still rely on. CCMT innovation can contribute directly to economic growth through its positive short and medium-term effects (Cervantes et al., 2023). Indirectly, the local development of environmental innovations helps reduce emissions (Bianchini et al., 2023), which, in turn, leads to positive economic outcomes across all time horizons at various spatial scales. For example, (i) innovations leading to efficient resource and energy use can result in cost reduction and increased competitiveness on firm level (Ghisetti and Rennings, 2014), (ii) increased productivity at the firm level in the case of lower local air pollution (Curci et al., 2023, find positive links between air pollution and workplace accidents), (iii) temperature rise due to global warming can harm economic growth in already warm countries (Diftenbaugh and Burke, 2019).²² Trying to mitigate further rise would be especially beneficial for developing countries.

In the following, we show with examples, how the knowledge space and relatedness measures together with countries' knowledge bases can be used to gain information on their existing innovation and their potential to innovate in certain CCMTs (for more details,

²² Some cold and mainly developed countries have benefited from temperature rise due to global warming. As most developing countries are harmed in economic terms by global temperature rise, this exaggerates global economic inequality (Diftenbaugh and Burke, 2019).

largest number of patents (1067,472) and hence shows the largest node size. Technological classes H04, H01 and A61 follow in the rank of technological activities. These classes represent, respectively, electric communication techniques, basic electric elements, and medical or veterinary science and hygiene.²⁵

The network is visualised using the ForceAtlas algorithm from Gephi developed by Mathieu Jacomy. The algorithm identifies highly connected nodes and repels them from each other while attracting those nodes they are connected to. Since the edges are weighted by each country's depreciated patent stock in each technological class, as previously outlined, the algorithm uses also the edge weights to determine the attraction force. This means that, *ceteris paribus*, countries with larger patent stocks in a particular technological class are pulled more strongly towards that class than those with smaller patent stocks.

This representation helps in visualising key points of this research. First, large developed countries are in a central position in the middle of the network (in pink). On the contrary, smaller and less developed countries take the peripheral position, at the bottom of the graph (in dark purple), as their patenting activities are much lower and are hence pulled less strongly towards technological classes.

Second, the network indicates the technological classes where innovation is easier (i.e., classes closer to the name of the country) and those where it is more complex (i.e., those further from the name of the country). The former are classes where developing countries also hold a significant share of patents, positioning them at the centre/bottom of the graph, between the cluster of developing and the cluster of developed countries. These technological classes are related to electricity (H), chemistry and metallurgy (C), and physics (G). The most complex technological classes, where innovation is challenging and patenting is scarce are depicted at the top of the graph, close to developed countries only. Most CCMTs lie close to technological classes from CPC-class B (performing operations; transporting). This includes classes related to tools and machines for manufacturing (such as B33) as well as transportation means such as aircraft, aviation and cosmonautics (B64), which is neighboured by its highly related Y02T90 class (including CCMTs related to transportation).

To explain how the knowledge space in Fig. 9 works, we visualise the ego-network for two CPC-class within the knowledge space in Fig. 10: one more complex class (B64), where developed countries may be specialized, and one less advanced class (E21), where developing countries may be specialized. In the left panel, B64 occupies a middle-upper position in the network indicating strong connections with leading innovators. The only developing country connected to this class is UAE, because of its strong position in the aviation market with Emirates Airlines. On the other hand, E21 (Earth Drilling; Mining), is shown in the right panel of the Figure and is placed in the bottom left/middle of the network. This class is connected with some developed countries as well as developing countries, rich in natural energy reserves such as Belarus, Iran, and Azerbaijan and Latin American countries such as Chile, Colombia and Argentina. This shows that less complex technological classes are linked to more developing countries.

Third, we can analyse countries' innovation patterns relative to each other and identify which countries yield similar positions in the knowledge space in Fig. 9. Top innovators like Germany, Japan, Switzerland, Canada, the UK, and China are centrally positioned. On the contrary, many Eastern European and Latin countries fall towards the lower right side. Argentina, Costa Rica and Colombia are located close to the bottom right. Hungary, Poland, the Czech Republic and Portugal are relatively central but below the main innovators. Moving further down, we find Romania, Slovenia, Latvia and Lithuania, indicating decreasing patenting activities. Countries with the least patenting activity, yet still connected to the main component, are in the very bottom right, including Kyrgyzstan, Albania, North Korea or Jordan and several small island states.

Fourth, the knowledge space helps to pinpoint those CCMTs where many developing countries already contribute with patents. Examples include Y02E10 (renewable energy), Y02E60 (energy technologies with potential or indirect contribution to cut GHG emissions), Y02W30 (CCMTs in solid waste management), as well as Y02A40 and Y02A50 (climate change adaptation technologies related to livestock, agriculture and extreme weather events). These classes are centrally located in the network because both developing and developed countries contribute to innovation in these areas. CCMTs where almost exclusively developed countries or the largest innovators contribute include technologies related to combustion technologies with mitigation potential (Y02E20) or ICTs related to e.g. low-power processors, power or thermal management (Y02D10), located further above.

The knowledge space gives a general overview of the current patenting landscape of countries and their relative position to each other. However, it does not clearly indicate which CCMTs are related to this knowledge. To understand this, one must examine the relatedness of the knowledge base of a country to a CCMT class. For example, important CCMT innovations for carbon capture and storage (Y02C20 class) are positioned far from most developing countries in the knowledge space (left periphery/ middle height). Argentina does not have a relative competitive advantage in this class, nor a significant number of patents. However, its knowledge base is related to it, indicating its potential for innovation in this field (see online network "CCMT-potential" from Appendix A.11).

Fig. 11 illustrates the concept, representing the relatedness density of countries in specific CCMTs, i.e. their *CCMT-potential*. The six panels depict the ego-networks of the top polluters in CO₂, i.e., China, US, India, Russia, Japan, and Iran, according to GCA (2021). These ego-networks are based on a two-mode network (called "CCMT-potential") connecting countries to CCMT classes based on their 5-year mean relatedness density in 2018.²⁶ Consider the case of three large economies specialised in their product portfolios (Iran, Russia and India): Iran and Russia are focused on highly debated industries that produce substantial emissions, while India specializes in a relatively new industry, that could be a steppingstone for other industries to become more sustainable. Therefore, their knowledge bases are related to many CCMTs. In contrast, countries like the US and Japan, are not necessarily specialised in industries with a clear link to climate change-related issues and hence their knowledge bases show less relatedness to CCMTs.

Fig. 11 also captures which specific CCMTs classes are related to a country. Iran (bottom right panel) specialises in the exports of

²⁵ See Appendix A.2 for a full list of the size of a technological class in terms of the number of patent applications linked to it.

²⁶ The full network is available as an interactive version online under the name *CCMT-potential* following instructions in Appendix A.11.

Fig. 10. Ego-networks for the CPC-classes B64 (left) and E21 (right). Ego-networks stem from the knowledge space that connects countries to technological classes based on their cumulative patent-stock in 2018, and show which countries are connected to the selected class within the knowledge space. (Visualisation of the network using the Force Atlas algorithm in Gephi 0.9.6).

Fig. 11. The CCMT-potential of countries; Ego-networks of the top 6 polluters according to GCA (2021) highlighted. Ego-networks stem from the network CCMT-potential, that connects countries to CCMT classes with edge weights corresponding to countries' relatedness densities to CCMT classes in 2018; From top left to bottom right: China, US, India, Russia, Japan, Iran. (Visualisation of the network using the Force Atlas algorithm in Gephi 0.9.6).

Ethylene Polymers (e.g. PE), used for plastic bags, toys and container production (Lab, 2023). Innovations in this class are mainly attributed to the technological classes C08 (macromolecular compounds) or B29 (working of plastics). In the technology space, both classes connect to multiple CCMTs related to the production or processing of goods, starting with the CPC code Y02P (e.g. Y02P20, for chemistry industry Y02P40 for mineral processing, and Y02P80 for sector-wide applications). These CCMTs are highlighted as promising to yield innovations in the ego-network. Plastic contributes at many stages of its production to GHG emissions (Cabernard et al., 2022) making CCMT innovation along the value chain possible, from input choices of bio-PE or energy type, to partial substitution of plastic in the final product. While relatedness to these Y02-classes is expected, it may be less obvious that Iran's knowledge base is also related to ICT technologies in energy-efficient computing (Y02D10).

Russia (bottom-left panel) is a major exporter of petroleum and metal products. Consequently, the main CCMT classes related to Russia's knowledge base are in the energy sector (Y02E) and transportation (Y02T). This is partly due to the CPC class C22, which covers the production and refining of metals and alloys. C22 is highly connected to CCMTs in transportation equipment (Y02T). Both petroleum and metal production are significant sources of emissions. Russia's specialization in these sectors means it also has the potential to develop CCMTs related to them. Fig. 11 confirms this and shows that the knowledge base of Russia is related to CCMTs in metal processing (Y02P10) and the petrochemical industry (Y02P30). Van den Berge et al. (2020) show, using a sample of EU regions from 1987 to 2010, that specialisation in fossil fuel technologies positively impacted the development of cleantech. However, whether this also holds in the Russian case depends not only on a country's relatedness to CCMTs, but also, for example, on the resistance to a green transition, which can stem from economic actors, as well as from institutional and infrastructural barriers.

Lastly, as a prominent offshoring destination, India (top-right panel) excels in service industries. Four out of the 15 CCMTs related to India's knowledge base are in Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) (Y02D), which have significant potential for improving energy efficiency. Currently, only a few countries have knowledge bases related to green ICTs and India is one of the few connected to all Y02D classes simultaneously.

Table 5 displays the top 3 CCMT classes related to the knowledge bases of Albania, Lebanon, Venezuela, Yemen and South Africa. South Africa, in comparison to the other four countries, has the highest degrees of relatedness in its top 3 CCMTs with all three relatedness densities exceeding 80 % (considering it is also the most active country in patenting among the list). The top CCMT class for Syria is only 22.8 % related to its knowledge base due to holding fewer RTAs in technological classes. CCMT class Y02P10 includes technologies related to the processing of metal and shows relatedness to Venezuela's and Albania's knowledge base. Main exports of Venezuela contain scrap Iron and Aluminium. For Albania the main exports are ferroalloys and crude oil, which also explains its high relatedness to Y02P30 (CCMTs related to oil refinement). Lebanon, with main economic activities in agriculture, is highly related to CCMTs for the adaptation to climate change in efficient water management and agriculture, forest and livestock.

The innovation activity of developing countries surrounding human necessities (A) is also reflected by the position of the countries in the knowledge space, which are in proximity to many A-classes (Fig. 9). Additionally, Y02P and Y02W classes appear in Table 5 very often, highlighting relatively strong relatedness to developing countries' knowledge bases with respect to other CCMT classes. The two classes encompass CCMTs related to (a) the production and processing of goods and (b) wastewater treatment or waste management, respectively. This mirrors the positioning of developing countries in global value chains where literature has found a relatively downstream position of developing countries in the production process with respect to developed countries (e.g. De Marchi et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2020).

Overall, we provide an initial intuitive description of the technological classes in which countries are more likely to innovate. However, the predictive value of this analysis is uncertain due to the aggregated nature of the data used. Countries that appear close in the knowledge space may still differ significantly in their likelihood to innovate, influenced by political and institutional factors that the knowledge space and the analysis of related CCMTs to a country's knowledge base cannot capture.

6. Conclusion and discussion

Using global patent data and a mixture model estimation, we investigate whether theories on regional technological relatedness and path dependencies in the development of new innovation hold at the country level and are different for developing and developed countries. We show that relatedness of CCMTs to a country's knowledge base (relatedness density) predicts (1) the probability of technological entry of a CCMT class into a country, and (2) (if technological entry occurs) the number of patents this country produces in the CCMT class. We find that the effect of relatedness density is stronger for developing countries, mainly for entry into the development of a CCMT, while the difference between developed and developing countries concerning intensity is small. A stronger effect for developing countries indicates that they have been developing CCMTs along a development path that is related to their local knowledge bases more than developed ones. We also find that innovation in CCMTs is facilitated by high levels of human capital.

We construct a novel dataset that maps the global knowledge space, positioning countries in relationship with different technological classes. This allows for a descriptive analysis, uncovering innovative strength of countries relative to each other and to different technological classes. Finally, by using relatedness densities we identify CCMTs that are related to a country's knowledge base, highlighting the CCMTs where countries are more likely to innovate.

The analysis has some limitations related to the use of patent data. First, patent data may fail to capture non-technological capabilities present in a country. Second, while patent data can be a proxy for innovations, it is difficult to measure whether an innovation is also implemented, and at what scale adoption takes place. Third, the propensity to patent differs across technological fields and countries. Many of our main variables rely on relative measures as opposed to pure comparisons of patent counts. Therefore, this is less of a concern, especially in the models where we additionally control for countries' propensity to patent as well as patenting propensity in specific technological domains. However, the issue remains in pure comparisons of patent counts (e.g. in the knowledge

Table 5

Top 3 CCMT classes with the highest relatedness to a country's knowledge base; For a sample of five developing countries.

Country	Class	Description	Relatedness	
Albania	AL	Y02P30	CCMTs in production/processing of goods; related to oil refining/petrochemical industry	26.04
		Y02T10	CCMTs related to road transport of goods or passengers	11.77
		Y02P10	CCMTs in production/processing of goods; related to metal processing	9.25
Lebanon	LB	Y02W10	CCMTs for wastewater treatment	76.93
		Y02A20	CC adaptation technologies: water conservation; efficient water supply; efficient water use	47.52
		Y02A40	Adaptation technologies in agriculture, forestry, livestock or agroalimentary production	42.92
Venezuela	VE	Y02P10	CCMTs in production/processing of goods; related to metal processing	46.00
		Y02W30	CCMTs for solid waste management	29.85
		Y02P40	CCMTs in production/processing of goods; related to the processing of minerals	27.56
Syria	SY	Y02B30	CCMTs related to buildings; energy efficient heating, ventilation or air conditioning	22.83
		Y02A20	CC adaptation technologies: water conservation; efficient water supply; efficient water use	18.17
		Y02E10	Reduction of GHG emissions: related to energy generation renewable energy sources	10.54
South Africa	ZA	Y02W10	CCMTs for wastewater treatment	92.02
		Y02E50	Reduction of GHG emissions; technologies for the production of fuel of non-fossil origin	84.27
		Y02A20	CC adaptation technologies: water conservation; efficient water supply; efficient water use	83.51

space that is based on patent counts or ranking of countries based on patenting activity).

Another limitation regards the use of relatedness measures to find promising avenues to innovate for two reasons First, many factors other than relatedness (e.g. institutional, historical, geographical factors) can explain whether innovation takes place, and relatedness can be seen as a factor that facilitates it, rather than determines it. Therefore, the analysis of the knowledge space in [Section 5](#) and the results of the regression analysis are only indicative and must be seen as a first step to explore the innovation potential of a country.

Last, highly related innovation trajectories to existing knowledge are associated with more incremental innovations ([Castaldi et al., 2015](#)), which are thought to have limited potential for climate change mitigation as compared to radical and breakthrough technologies. Thus, our research disregards one important pathway to innovation. However, incremental innovation may be particularly beneficial for developing countries because: (1) it is more likely to be successful (2) it is more realistically attainable within the available financial constraints, and (3) it is more likely to be adopted and further diffused. On the contrary, radical innovations require substantial financial involvement from third parties, including potentially financially constrained governments.

Therefore, we call for more systematic research on the ability of developing countries to contribute to radical green innovations and green breakthrough innovations, and on the identification of the main financial providers of such projects.

Additionally, future research should consider three modifications to our approach. First, we construct the knowledge base by using knowledge produced within a country's own borders, without considering diffused technologies and thus spillovers. Research has shown that (a) strong international trade links between countries facilitate the diffusion of R&D ([Xu and Wang, 2000](#); [Consoli et al., 2023](#); [Costantini et al., 2023](#)) that can add to a country's knowledge base and (b) the diversification paths of countries are through knowledge spillovers related to neighbouring countries knowledge bases ([Bahar et al., 2014](#)). Including these two factors in the knowledge base is left for future research. Second, investigating spatial differences in technological relatedness is a promising avenue of research (see [Boschma, 2017](#), for a review). We assume static technological relatedness across space, without examining how it varies across countries. Doing so would make the measure of technological relatedness imprecise.²⁷ Third, future research could consider how CCMTs impact climate change, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions or the degree of adaptation to adverse effects of climate change. However, measuring the environmental impact is difficult in general and patent data does not contain information about it.

This research gives policymakers a viewpoint on CCMT innovation in developing countries. The positioning of each developing country in the global knowledge space can help identify local capabilities, which developing countries already possess and that could be harvested in a more efficient way.

Author statement

The authors declare that:

- the work described has not been published previously.
- the article is not under consideration for publication elsewhere.
- the article's publication is approved by all authors and tacitly or explicitly by the responsible authorities where the work was carried out.

²⁷ The advantage of using pooled patent data across years and countries is robustness in the measure of technological relatedness. The disadvantage of doing so is the possibility of imprecise measurement of technological relatedness.

- if accepted, the article will not be published elsewhere in the same form, in English or in any other language, including electronically without the written consent of the copyright-holder.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Franziska Tinnefeld: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Julia Swart:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Elena Fumagalli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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